

PRODUCER IN A RELATIONSHIP WITH SUBJECTS OF COPYRIGHT AND RELATED RIGHTS

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Annotation: The article reveals the essence and specificity of creative industries as a unique socio-cultural phenomenon, the mechanism for implementing modern art strategies, the resource of the socio-economic potential of the territories. The author notes that the most important resource of creative entrepreneurship - production as a type of entrepreneurial activity in the art industry / art business - is art management, which is the philosophy and culture of management in the sphere of art.

Keywords: creative industries, creativity, creative economy, artistic strategies, creative entrepreneurship, art business, art management

Абстрактный: В статье раскрывается сущность и специфика творческих индустрий как уникального социокультурного феномена, механизма реализации современных арт-стратегий, ресурса социально-экономического потенциала территорий. Автор констатирует, что важнейшим ресурсом творческого предпринимательства – продюсерства как вида предпринимательской деятельности в арт-индустрии/арт-бизнесе, является арт-менеджмент, который есть философия и культура управления в сфере искусства.

Ключевые слова: творческие индустрии, креативность, творческая экономика, арт-стратегии, творческое предпринимательство, арт-бизнес, артменеджмент

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ijodiy sohalarning noyob ijtimoiy-madaniy hodisa, zamonaviy san'at strategiyalarini amalga oshirish mexanizmi, hududlarning

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy salohiyati resursi sifatidagi mohiyati va o'ziga xosligi ochib berilgan. Muallif ijodiy tadbirkorlikning eng muhim resursi - ishlab chiqarish san'at sanoatida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining bir turi sifatida / san'at biznesi san'at sohasidagi menejment falsafasi va madaniyati bo'lgan badiiy menejment ekanligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijodiy industriyalar, ijodkorlik, ijodiy iqtisodiyot, badiiy strategiyalar, ijodiy tadbirkorlik, san'at biznesi, san'at boshqaruvi

Many talented people (poets, writers, musicians, musicians, stage directors, actors) live in our country and abroad, whose work deserves the attention of listeners, readers, and viewers. Through the Internet, in particular through various social networks, aspiring musicians, writers or directors can bring their art to the general public. However, sooner or later there comes a moment when intellectual, creative work must bring a certain income, because you can't earn much money from performances in clubs and private shows. A creative person needs the help of another person to develop his creative and, in the future, commercial potential - a producer, whose legal status raises many questions.

Who is a producer? A subject who solves organizational issues in the process of recording albums, concert performances (music producer), creates conditions for creating films (film producer), responsible for the creative component of the project (creative producer)? What does a producer have in common with a phonogram maker?

In existing electronic sources, the following definition exists: a producer (English producer - manufacturer, commodity producer, manufacturer) is a specialist who takes direct participation in the production of the project, regulates (or helps to regulate) the financial, administrative, technological, creative or legal aspects of the activity, regulates the policy in the implementation of any project [1].

For example, in accordance with Art. 1 of the Law of Ukraine "On Copyright and Related Rights", a producer of an audiovisual work is a person who organizes or organizes and finances the creation of an audiovisual work [2]. Researcher S.A.

Slobodyan offers his own definition: a producer is a person who organizes or organizes and finances the creation of an audiovisual work or the performance of a work of literature or art [3].

At first glance, both the producer as a person who organized the creation of an audio-visual work and the producer of a phonogram have a common feature - the organization of the creation of objects of copyright and related rights. However, in the first case, we are talking about creating an audiovisual work, in the second - about creating a recording of sounds.

Based on the legal definitions of the concepts of "audiovisual work" and "phonogram", we can conclude that the concept of audiovisual works are much broader than a phonogram. An audiovisual work implies not only the presence of sound, but also a set of images. Consequently, the legislator rightly classifies cinematographic works as such. A phonogram is just a recording of sounds.

This, considering a producer as a person who organized the creation of an audiovisual work and a phonogram producer through the prism of objects of copyright (audiovisual work) and related rights (phonogram), we can logically assume that a producer has broader organizational functions compared to a phonogram producer. Consequently, the organization of the creation of an audiovisual work implies work not only with sound, but also with other materials necessary to create a work. However, we are interested in the creative contribution of the producer; organization, whatever it may be, is not creativity. Consequently, the creative element cannot be singled out. Another question arises: why is the producer of an audiovisual work called a producer and does he get the right to use the work on the basis of contracts with the authors, while the law calls the producer of a phonogram a subject of related rights and gives him the exclusive right to a phonogram? Consider a producer and a phonogram producer from the point of view of the scope of their exclusive rights.

In accordance with paragraph 4 of Art. 1263 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, the manufacturer of an audiovisual work shall have the exclusive right

to the audiovisual work as a whole, unless otherwise follows from the agreements concluded by him with the authors of the audiovisual work. The producer, in any use of an audiovisual work, has the right to indicate his name or designation or require such indication. In the absence of proof to the contrary, the producer of an audiovisual work is the person whose name or designation is indicated on this work in the usual way. The rights of the producer of an audiovisual work, that is, the person who organized the creation of this work (producer), are determined in accordance with Art. 1240 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation.

Let us turn to paragraph 1 of Art. 1240 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation. A person who has organized the creation of a complex object that includes several protected results of intellectual activity (film, other audiovisual work, theatrical performance, multimedia product, database) acquires the right to use these results on the basis of agreements on the alienation of the exclusive right or license agreements concluded such person with the owners of exclusive rights to the relevant results of intellectual activity.

This, based on the content of Art. 1263 and 1240 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, we can note that the producer acquires a derivative right from those exclusive rights of each of the authors transferred to him under the contract. In addition, Art. 1240 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, the term “producer” itself is not used, instead it is indicated “the person who organized the creation of a complex object, including several protected results of intellectual activity”. Therefore, the following questions arise: why in Art. 1240 the legislator did not apply the concept <<producer>> and is it possible to reduce the legislative definition of a producer to a person who organized the creation of a complex object that includes several protected results of intellectual activity?

Within the meaning of Art. 1324 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, the producer of a phonogram has the exclusive right to use the phonogram in any way that does not contradict the law. In accordance with Art. 1229 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, to which Art. 1324, the producer of the phonogram may, at

his discretion, permit or prohibit others from using the phonogram. Thus, from the point of view of rights in relation to objects, intellectual property (audiovisual work and phonogram) about producer and phonogram producer are endowed with exclusive rights, but on different grounds.

Important questions remain unanswered: if a producer is defined as a person who organized the creation of an audiovisual work, then what is the organizational moment and what is his creative contribution to the creation of such a work? By the way, among the authors of an audiovisual work, along with the director, scriptwriter and composer, there is no producer. Therefore, it should be noted that the legislator did not include the producer among the subjects of copyright, based on the fact that the producer is not the owner of the original copyright, but receives it under contracts, that is, he is the owner of exclusive rights already derived from it.

Regarding the organization of the creation of an audiovisual work, it is important to analyze the immediate responsibilities of the producer. Specialists who study the content of the contract between the musician and the producer note that the producer's duties should include the following activities [5]:

- involvement of directors, screenwriters, artists, sound engineers, pyrotechnicians and other persons in the stage work [6];
- organization of the rehearsal process, maintenance and improvement of professional form (vocal, choreographic, performing body and acting skills, physical form) and skills of the artist (team);
- provision of concert activities, other public performances (participation in broadcasts and programs of on-air and cable broadcasting organizations, media interviews); recording a video clip, organizing a photo shoot, ensuring the protection of the artist (group);
- recording and subsequent use of phonograms and audiovisual works, creation and use of objects of copyright and/or related rights;
- advertising of the artist (collective);
- the creation of a musical group (if the artist does not perform solo) and the organization of its activities as a commercial project, the development of the concept

of such activities, the formulation of long-term plans, the approval of schedules for the activities of the group in the field of variety and show business; formation of stage and public images of a musical group and its members;

- involvement of teachers, make-up artists, hairdressers, stylists and other specialists of similar specialties; providing accommodation for art one hundred (team); - representing the interests of the artist (collective) and negotiating on the most favorable terms for the parties to the contract; organization of the participation of an artist (musical group) in advertising campaigns of manufacturers of goods, works and services, using his appearance and (or) his works, PERFORMED by them.

Based on this far from complete indicative list of duties, producer, it can be concluded that the specific duties of a producer maybe the most diverse, being prescribed in the contract. With the organization of the creation of an audiovisual work and another complex object that includes several protected results of intellectual activity, the picture is clear, but the question remains about the creative contribution of the producer in the creation of such works: what to do if the invited producer is not ONLY creates conditions for musicians to record songs? If the producer's participation is not limited to organizational and technical work, but he, together with the musicians, arranges, builds the sound, mixes the recorded instruments and vocals, then, therefore, it can be said with certainty that the producer is engaged in creative activities and can be considered one of the authors of the musical work. Accordingly, in this case, the producer will act as the subject of copyright. Therefore, according to the researchers, in accordance with the producer agreement, it is advisable to provide that the producer acquires copyright for the use of the corresponding musical work by concluding bilateral copyright agreements with copyright holders, which may be the artist (kollekture). However, the producer will be the owner of derivative copyright or related rights. Thus, depending on the content of such agreements, the producer may retain both exclusive copyright and related rights.

Bibliographic list

1. URL: <http://ru.wikipedia.org/>
2. Law of Ukraine "On Copyright and Related Rights" dated July 11, 2001 No. 2627
URL: <http://www.copyright.ru/>
3. Slobodyan S.A. Related rights of performers and their correlation with the rights of authors and producers // Reklama i pravo. 2009. No. 1. S. 26-27.
4. Civil Code of the Russian Federation. Part four of 18 Dec. 2006 No. 230-FZ (as amended on December 31, 2014) // Ros. gas. Dec 22, 2006
5. Kryazhev V. Producer's contract with a musician: what to look for // Intellectual property: Copyright and related rights. 2014. No. 9. S. 20-31.
6. Agency agreement for the provision of producer services (sample). URL: <http://www.artparovoz/432>